

**PERCEIVING THE DIVINITY
OF THE ASSYRIAN KING:
TWO OBSERVATIONS FROM THE SIDELINES
ON A RECENT BOOK BY JULIAN E. READE¹⁾**

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Abstract

The Palace of Ashurbanipal at Nineveh has recently been the biographical subject of a monograph by Julian Edgeworth Reade. This discussion uses Reade's analyses to examine the new ways through which the last Assyrian kings presented themselves. The observations are built on the peculiar architectural traits of the palace's throneroom and the upper rooms. It is concluded that the innovations introduced by Ashurbanipal contributed to turn the image of the king into a quasi-divine entity, with the consequence that Greek sources judged the Assyrian kings as unseen gods.

Introduction

The royal palaces of first-millennium Assyria—the actual seats of kingship and the physical manifestation of the king's court—have been the subject of several scholarly studies. Since their first systematic excavations in the nineteenth century, there has been a steadily growing interest in the Assyrian palaces that have produced an enormous variety of interpretations over the years. The architecture of the royal palaces and the record of visual representations and inscriptions they contain have allowed scholars to reconstruct the kings' personalities and their tastes, understand their ideological choices and political mechanisms, and mine the decorative programs for insights into Assyrian visual culture. The different approaches which scholars have developed have thus plumbed the micro- and macrocosms of the Assyrian royal palace reality and Assyrian history more generally. Irrespective of their approach, these studies have also given special attention to those seminal works which, especially from the early 1970s, started to provide us with a biography of the Assyrian palaces. These meticulous works attempted to provide a reconstruction of the palaces' architecture, their construction techniques and building phases, their use and reuse over time, and the careful positioning of reliefs within their original architectural settings. In this academic landscape, the prolific scientific production of Julian Edgeworth Reade represents one of the most important contributions. Reade has contributed significantly to the field and any research on the Assyrian world will significantly rely on his authoritative and trustworthy work. The future tense is used here deliberately because his astonishing contribution, as stated in the Festschrift dedicated to him, will always be

worth reading and rereading.³⁾ The length and breadth of his publications is an absolute asset for any Near Eastern scholar, and, through the incessant nature of his commitment, Reade continues to offer precious scientific analyses to the academic community.

The book *Design and Destruction: The Palace of Ashurbanipal at Nineveh* represents Reade's most recent feat, in which he assesses and synthesizes the primary evidence to reconstruct and write a history of the North Palace of Ashurbanipal at Nineveh. This is a work that has never been done before and yet has long been a scholarly desideratum. Reade approaches his subject by proposing a biography of the palace, which starts from its construction relying on textual evidence (Chapter 2). This is followed by a detailed history of the excavations, which are carefully retraced through passages extracted from nineteenth-century letters and diaries, together with their date and location (Chapter 3). Combining these excerpts with the available archaeological evidence, Reade then examines the structure (Chapter 4), the ground plan and organization (Chapter 5) of the North Palace, highlighting elements of tradition, continuity, and innovation, and proposing adjustments to previous works where necessary. The longest and most complex sections of Reade's analysis examine the mural decoration of the palace, focusing on the state apartments (Chapter 6), the corridors and the postern gate (Chapter 7), and the upper rooms (Chapters 8–9). These chapters do not focus on describing the wall reliefs, for which other works already exist, but on a technical analysis of these reliefs, their measurements, and the details of their edges; an attempt is made to assign them to their original positions, reconstruct their associations with the palace spaces, and interpret their interrelationships. Questions concerning the dates of the wall reliefs are also discussed throughout the book, but are usefully summarized for the reader in a dedicated chapter (Chapter 10), along with a description of the “selective disfigurement” (56) that some of the sculptures suffered during the sack of the North Palace (Chapter 11) and their final dispersal in national museums and private collections after the discovery of the palace (Chapter 12). Finally, Reade concludes his book by orienting scholars towards the next desirable endeavors to fully dissect and understand the Assyrian palaces (Chapter 13). These last pages pave the way for further research and represent a generous gift offered by a distinguished and brilliant scholar to students and academics who will embark on similar praiseworthy endeavors.

About half of the volume concerns the mural decoration and its assessment and reorganization. The meticulousness which characterizes this section is impressive and hypothetical reconstructions are always proposed with caution, although in many cases these appear very reliable. As in his previous publications, Reade impeccably combines an understanding of architectural settings with an accurate art historical analysis of the wall reliefs. There is no preconception or bias in the author's approach, as it may happen when dealing with the Assyrian Empire: the topic is very technical, and it is clearly evident throughout the book that the author inductively infers information on the palace layout and its wall-panels, offering reasonable and grounded outcomes. Considering the uncertainty or total loss relating to some

¹⁾ READE, J.E. — *Design and Destruction: The Palace of Ashurbanipal at Nineveh* (Archiv für Orientforschung, Beiheft 34). Institut für Orientalistik, Vienna, 2022 (30 cm, VI, 112, 78 figs.). ISBN 978-3-900345-14-3. ISSN 1015-3403. € 44,-.

²⁾ This paper is part of the project GALATEO – Good Attitudes for Life in Assyrian Times: Etiquette and Observance of Norms in Male and Female Groups, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101027543. The information contained in this article reflects only the author's views.

³⁾ For a thorough bibliography, see Finkel / Simpson 2020.

rooms (e.g., Upper Rooms, on pages 23, 36–53), their classification and position can be proposed by size, scale, and subject-matter only. In this regard, Reade's suggestions are well-thought-out, and reservations or alternatives are always prudently proposed (e.g., on pages 39, 42, or 51). Reade also relies on the “techniques of traditional scholars” (66), without adopting new specific methodological approaches. And yet, his approach reveals itself to be fruitful in underscoring the “complicated process of design” (24) of an Assyrian palace and, in particular, the elaboration of scenes carved on the wall-panels. The result is an extremely polished work that represents a massive effort by the author. All libraries covering the ancient Near East should acquire it.

This is not the place to examine in detail all of the analyses and ideas proposed by the author. Alternative hypotheses might be suggested in the future, but the validity of his proposals does not need to be re-evaluated or questioned. Instead, I would like to back up two of Reade's acute archaeological reconstructions—which are, in my view, built on objective and crystal-clear evidence—with some additional comments or further proofs stemming from an examination of the textual and iconographic sources.

Ashurbanipal as an “Unseen God”

In the chapter focusing on the “Ground Plan and Organization of the North Palace” (Chapter 5), Reade highlights the unusual lay-out of Room M, the throneroom of the palace, both of whose ends are separated from the rest of the room by short wall-stubs or jambs. This feature is found in the South-West Palace of Esarhaddon at Nimrud (Kertai 2015: figs. 7.1–7.2), where two rooms alongside one another share the spaces at each end. A remarkable detail in the palace of Esarhaddon is the presence, found in between each of the four wall-stubs, of what appear to be column-bases. In light of these elements and the attestations of columns elsewhere in the North Palace, Reade hypothesizes that columns may have existed at both ends of Room M as well and, following previous works, that the space beyond the wall-stubs or jambs may have been occupied by the throne. This would imply that the king received guests in a secluded alcove, further removed from people.⁴ Interestingly, we are informed that bull colossi in reliefs flanked the two wall-stubs in Esarhaddon's palace (Kertai 2015: 156–158), and may have been arranged in this manner in Ashurbanipal's palace, although this point remains hypothetical (19).

Such a change in the lay-out represents a remarkable departure from the traditional Assyrian throneroom and it is possible that it was an architectural tradition adopted from the south or an indigenous development, as has already been suggested elsewhere (Roaf 1973: 87). It is also likely, as touched upon by Reade, that this change may be related to the way in which the last Assyrian kings “retreated from public exposure” (19). Expanding on this hypothesis, it is reasonable to believe that this was a direct consequence and a physical manifestation of the political upheavals and bloody events featuring at the end of Sennacherib's reign, which concluded with his murder (Parpola 1980), and especially was a part of the precautions taken by Esarhaddon during his

⁴ In general, columns appear to be a new introduction of the seventh century BCE, together with sphinxes and statues used as column bases (Kertai 2017: 100).

accession to the throne and during his reign, whose conspiracies led the king to strengthen security measures (Radner 2003; 2010).⁵ Similar changes might also be connected to the king's health conditions that had to be kept hidden from prying eyes (Radner 2003), or simply to his apprehensive personality that led him to eccentric forms of behaviors (Ermidoro 2014: 85–86) because of his fear for potential threats from demons, or disease transmissions, as a consequence of his possible participation in his father's assassination.⁶ These precautions were probably inherited and even expanded by Ashurbanipal. Therefore, one can suspect that proximity of people to the king was potentially dangerous and distance equaled safety accordingly.

But other factors can also be highlighted. The addition of a new fixed feature in the throneroom may have had a profound impact on the relationships between the Assyrian king and his people, including palatial residents and external visitors. The new distance from the king was considerably increased and the physical separation was created not only by the throne, but also by the distinction between spaces: king and people were physically separated, such that they essentially belonged to two different rooms and thus to two well-distinguished physical realities. If we also consider the presence of mediators and guards, we may speculate that the distance from the king was perhaps almost ten meters (Reade 2022: fig. 15), with the consequence that no one could hear the king's voice, unless he exaggerated or amplified it. This implied that much of the nonverbal communication shifted to gestures and body postures (Bull / Doody 2013), that the whole figure of the king may have been seen as quite small or, at least, that intimate visual details in the face were not perceived and nobody could touch him (Hall 1966). All these aspects relating to the physical distance had psychological implications on the subjects' thoughts and feelings, judgments, and emotional states; in this way, the king was perceived as an attainable figure, both physically and visually, but one detached from the rest of his people. In addition, the king could no longer receive direct sunlight, as in the previous thronerooms (Portuese 2019: 77–78). Thus he was kept in the gloomy alcove, unless it was lit by artificial light sources. In the latter case, the mysterious fascination surrounding the royal persona would even be increased.

Interestingly, in conjunction with this change, a variation in adulatory expressions used in royal correspondence could be a direct consequence of this architectural innovation. The expression that someone is going “to see the face of the king” (*pānī ša šarri bēlīya ammarūni*) occurs in letters sent to Sargon II and indicates that an actual meeting with the king is due to take place or has been requested.⁷ However, texts dating to Esarhaddon and Ashurbanipal's reigns very often speak of the ardent desire of courtiers to behold the face of the king, conveying the idea that it was considered

⁵ Among these measures, Radner (2003: 169–170) argues that people approaching the king had to be veiled. However, it is the king who was hidden and, with the exception of a much-debated letter (SAA 18 100), nowhere is it stated or shown that people had to be veiled when in front of the king or was the Assyrian king traditionally an unattainable figure or kept secluded (see Portuese 2020a in this respect). Esarhaddon and Ashurbanipal represent exceptional cases.

⁶ On Esarhaddon's involvement in Sennacherib's assassination, see Knapp 2020; Dalley / Siddall 2021; Portuese 2022.

⁷ SAA 1 131: r 8–r 14; SAA 5 47: r 1–r 4; SAA 5 294: r 8–r 13. All these attestations date to Sargon II's reign.

a great favor to be allowed to look at the king face to face.⁸⁾ Sources on this issue illustrate the emotional moment of being before the king Esarhaddon by using overly sentimental and affectionate words, such as the following: “the shadow of the king, my lord, is pleasant for everything. Let them come up and run around in the sweet and pleasant shadow of the king, my lord” (SAA 10 207: b.e. 20–r 5). These references strongly suggest that Esarhaddon was clearly distinguished from other people, both for his isolated or somehow unique position and his physical and aesthetic features (Portuese 2020a: 127–143). Such a position may well have been created by the new concealed area within the throneroom that physically detached the king from the rest of the room. This assumption can be extended to Ashurbanipal’s throneroom.

Although it is difficult to say whether these new architectural features were an imported element or an indigenous development, I would suggest that inspiration may have been drawn from temples. In Assyrian temples, there are usually two short walls projecting out on either side at the front of the sanctuary, the inmost recess or holiest part of the temple (Mallowan 1966 I: fig. 242; III: pl. 6; Reade 2002: 171; Neumann 2018: fig. 9). The sanctuary was located at the short end of a long room (anteroom) and, as a rule, a person would have had to turn on a bent axis in order to align himself or herself with the doorway to the sanctuary. The room did not receive sunlight and was essentially dark; it could be protected by otherworldly figures, especially lining the doorway of the anteroom (Reade 2002: fig. 47), and by statues representing divine attendants (Mallowan 1966 I: fig. 243). The divine statue—a combination of precious metals, stones, and textiles—stood on a raised dais located in the gloomy sanctuary. At the sensorial level, entering the darkness of the room, viewing the little light passing through the doorway and the radiant statue lit by a lamp light greatly impacted on the person’s senses and clearly fostered the notion of being in front of the mysterious and unattainable divine world (Neumann 2018).

Such a scenario, together with its accompanying emotive effects, does not seem to diverge too greatly from the one created by Esarhaddon and adopted by Ashurbanipal. The architectural setting introduced by Esarhaddon may thus reflect a change in court ceremonial practice that aimed at conveying a quasi-divine image of the king and turning the meeting with the king into a quasi-divine encounter at the sensorial level. The distance, both physical and psychological, and darkness contributed to reshape the perception of the Assyrian king as though he were a deity. In this light, it comes as no surprise that Esarhaddon is often described as being the perfect likeness of the god (SAA 10 207: r 12–r 13) or as the very image of Shamash (SAA 10 196: r 4–r 5),⁹⁾ while Ashurbanipal is depicted as having been chosen and raised by the gods: “I knew no father or mother, I grew up in the lap of my goddesses. As a child the great gods guided me, going with me on the right and the left” (SAA 3 3: 13–15).¹⁰⁾ Thus, as in temples, the physical seclusion of

the Assyrian king within the new alcove had the consequence that he was perceived as a deity without being officially divinized.

In this context, I feel inclined to further stress the profound repercussions that such an architectural adjustment to the court ceremonial practice had over time, especially regarding the perception that Greek authors construed and transmitted in relation to the Assyrian kings in describing royal court etiquette in Persia. Around the fifth and fourth centuries BCE, Ctesias of Cnidos, the court doctor to the Great King and the Persian royal family, attempted in his famous *Persica* to describe the nature of the Assyrian king, his seclusion in his palace, his abundance of luxury, his passivity before events, and his voluptuous character. As he writes: “For in the first place he spent all his time in the palace, seen by no one except his concubines and attendant eunuchs, and sought luxury and idleness and the total avoidance of suffering and anxiety, thinking that the goal of a happy reign was to enjoy every kind of pleasure without restraint. [...] And the fact that he was seen by no one outside the palace meant that everyone was ignorant of the extent of his luxurious lifestyle, and no one dared to speak ill of him through fear, as if he were an unseen god” (Ctesias, *Persica*, F1b, 21.2, 21.7).¹¹⁾ This description implies that the king possessed a cruel and fearful nature, being an invisible person who lives like an unseen god in an inaccessible building and whose access is strictly regulated or even hindered by the rhetorical etiquette of his court. Ctesias states that a certain king, Ninyas (a fictitious figure), son of Semiramis (the Assyrian queen Sammuamat, mother of Adad-nirari III), introduced the features of inaccessibility and invisibility to the king’s persona and refers to this aspect as a change in his personal behavior, although his successors up to the popular Sardanapalus (probably Ashurbanipal) also ruled in a similar way.

Likewise, Herodotus states that, through his personal inaccessibility and invisibility, Deioeces—the first Median king who freed Media from the Assyrian dominion—finally obtained a strong dominion, which Herodotus describes as “tyranny”. As he writes: “So Deioeces had this stronghold built for himself, surrounding his own residence, but he told the whole population to build their houses outside the stronghold. Once the building programme was completed, Deioeces was the first to establish the following rules: no one was to enter into the king’s presence, but all business was to be conducted through messengers; the king was to be seen by no one; and furthermore absolutely no one was to commit the offence of laughing or spitting in the king’s presence. The reason he instituted this grandiose system of how to behave in relation to himself was to prevent any of his peers seeing him. They had been brought up with him, their lineage was no worse than his, and they were just as brave as he was, so he was worried that if they saw him they might get irritated and conspire against him; on the other hand, if they could not see him, they might think that he had changed” (Herodotus, *The Histories*, Book 1, 99).¹²⁾

The fact that both Herodotus and Ctesias present negative views on Asian kings leads one to suspect that this emphasis on the inaccessibility and invisibility of the king may have been an exclusively Greek attitude and their negative judg-

⁸⁾ ABL 285: r 5–r 8; SAA 13 80: 11–r 14; SAA 13 190: r 16–r 18; SAA 16 37: 5–9; SAA 16 63: e. 2.

⁹⁾ Esarhaddon’s new architectural introduction may have also depended, among other things, on his illness, since later on in the letter it is stated that the king kept himself in the dark.

¹⁰⁾ See, among other examples, the prophecies for Ashurbanipal as crown prince (SAA 9 7).

¹¹⁾ Translation by Llewellyn-Jones / Robson 2010: 131.

¹²⁾ Translated by Waterfield 1998: 46–47.

ments were consequently the outcome of a specific ideological position, intended to depict the Persian kings as oppressive tyrants. Moreover, recent research (Portuese 2020a) has demonstrated how the Assyrian king was actually less secluded in his palace than was hitherto assumed by the classical tradition originating from Ctesias and followed by some modern scholars. However, in light of the above-mentioned changes, I would like to briefly reappraise the Greek perceptions of the Assyrian kings and unveil a possible kernel of truth underlying these apparent preconceptions.

Although apparently similar, the two authors diverge in two remarkable points.¹³⁾ First, Ctesias points to the Assyrian tradition and Herodotus to the Median tradition as the models on which the Achaemenid court protocol was built. Second, Ctesias states that Ninyas decided to conceal himself because of his vicious and cowardly personality and his luxurious and extravagant lifestyle that allowed him to avoid suffering and anxiety.¹⁴⁾ Herodotus, on the contrary, clearly points out that security reasons lie behind the king's physical self-distancing and isolation, because Deioeces basically feared his peers and their potential for conspiring against him. Because of this potential conspiracy and threat, Deioeces decided to hide from the people to protect himself. Therefore, invisibility, unattainability, and his different nature acted as a strategy to protect the royal persona.¹⁵⁾

At the same time, the two authors agree on three notable aspects. First, both Herodotus and Ctesias state that the king's detachment and invisibility were innovations introduced by individual kings due to specific historical circumstances rather than general traditions which characterized the "Oriental" kingship. This implies that the king's concealment was exceptional. Second, they both point to the fact that—especially in the case of Ninyas—the inaccessibility and invisibility of the king are consequences of an abrupt change in the court protocol. Third, they both describe the outcome of such a choice in a similar way: it led to a fearful atmosphere, where the king was perceived as an unseen god.

Taken altogether, all these elements indicate that both Ctesias and Herodotus are reporting on political and ideological circumstances that characterized the reigns of Esarhaddon and Ashurbanipal.¹⁶⁾ In fact, by combining their statements—on the king's extravagant personality, fear of threats, and his apprehension towards conspiracies and illnesses—it seems that Ctesias and Herodotus describe the real historical background featuring Esarhaddon and Ashurbanipal's reigns: these final Assyrian kings detached themselves from the people because they suspected their peers, and feared suffering and anxiety, and especially so in the case of Esarhaddon. The consequence of this is that a), by being secluded and less accessible, kings were believed to spend their days enjoying their own palaces and richness; and b), by being concealed in a gloomy and protected room like

a divine statue in a sanctuary, they were perceived as quasi-divine figures.¹⁷⁾

Ashurbanipal and Libbali-sharrat as a Mirror of the Divine Couple

From this latter aspect I would now like to turn to my second observation anchored in the new reconstruction proposed by Reade of the upper rooms of Ashurbanipal's palace (23).¹⁸⁾ In particular, I will focus on the reliefs that may once have decorated what Reade calls Room X (originally designated as Room S¹), which could have been roughly the same size and shape as the lower Room S. According to the revised classification of the fallen wall-panels (discussed in Reade's Chapter 8), Room X could have been lined by lion-killing scenes in three registers (groups FSA-1 to FSA-6 corresponding to X-1 to X-6) and a single composition in three linked registers, including the so-called Garden Scene (groups FSB-1 to FSB-9, corresponding to X-7 to X-15). The two groups of panels are similarly arranged in three registers and "the obvious hypothesis is that the two series both fell directly down from a single room, *i.e.* Room X" (42). Reade locates the first group on the north-west wall of Room X, with the relief series being divided by a window (X-1 to X-3, X-4 to X-6), while the second group may have occupied the full length of the opposite wall, the south-east wall, perhaps being interrupted by one or both of the doors of Room X that led into the hypothetical Rooms Y and Z.

This two-relief series has been extensively discussed in the past, and here I would like to review their subject-matter by considering Reade's reconstruction and Ashurbanipal's particular devotion to Nabu.¹⁹⁾ As has been pointed out by scholars, the royal hunt and the Garden Scene of Ashurbanipal are crammed with references to historical events, in the form of Ashurbanipal's victories, and mythological references, with many convincing readings having been suggested.²⁰⁾ An additional possibility, however, is that both the hunt and the Garden Scene were the visual adaptation of textual incidents concerning Nabu and Tashmetu.

Starting with the Garden Scene, the relief shows the Assyrian king Ashurbanipal reclining on a couch, while the queen Libbali-sharrat sits next to him in a lush garden, which might have belonged to the queen herself.²¹⁾ Now, as I have already discussed elsewhere, an initial comparison with this scene can be found in the *Love Lyrics of Nabû and Tašmetu* (SAA 3 14), the parallelisms with which are conspicuous.²²⁾ Firstly, the goddess offers protection to Nabu

¹³⁾ See Lanfranchi 2010 for a more comprehensive analysis on Ctesias and Herodotus' descriptions.

¹⁴⁾ See also the similar description of Sardanapalus' lifestyle offered by Ctesias (Llewellyn-Jones / Robson 2010: 133, 23.1–23.4).

¹⁵⁾ It can only be inferred that, by the expression "they might think that he had changed", Herodotus referred to the king's alleged divine nature (Lanfranchi 2010: 57).

¹⁶⁾ Lanfranchi (2010: 58–60) already underscored that the description of the apparent divine nature of the Assyrian king in Ctesias may reflect the actual tendency occurring in Esarhaddon and Ashurbanipal's documents to elevate the status of the Assyrian king and his special relationship with the divine world.

¹⁷⁾ Although this remains a matter of speculation, I would be tempted to see in the incense burners separating the Achaemenid king from his guests in audience scenes from Persepolis (Allen 2005) a direct echo of the column bases that once separated the Assyrian king from the subjects who sought audience with him.

¹⁸⁾ For a different interpretation of the upper rooms as rooms on the ground floor, see Kertai 2015: 179–180.

¹⁹⁾ In this respect, see Pomponio 1978: 80–83; Rubin 2021: 441–468.

²⁰⁾ Regarding the hunt reliefs coming from the upper rooms, see Watanabe 1992; 1998; and, more recently, Wagner-Durand 2019. For the Garden Scene, see especially Albenda 1976; 1977; Collins 2004; 2006; Gilibert 2018; Ataç 2018: 151–178; Kertai 2020; Portuese 2020b: 123–127; also Reade in his recent book, on page 40.

²¹⁾ Albenda 1976.

²²⁾ Here is presented an abridged version of the observations proposed. The original paper started life as a talk entitled "A Divine Love Affair in the Royal Garden: Etiquette and Morality of the Assyrian Queen" given at the Fifth Workshop on Gender, Methodology and the Ancient Near East

and he can find refreshment and protection under the shade of a sprig of juniper (SAA 3 14: 1–11), just like Ashurbanipal, who reclines on a couch under the shade and protection of trees and the vine arbor.²³) Interestingly, the plant held by Libbali-sharrat resembles a sprig of juniper, which is the very one mentioned in the text. In the love lyrics, once Nabu and Tashmetu are together, the physical intimacies they enjoy are described in terms of the garden and wisdom: the garden (*kiriū*) represents a perfect place for courting or love-making, being a hideaway and a beautiful setting, while the counterpart of the garden is the “tablet house” (Edubba), the dwelling of Nabu (SAA 3 14: 12–16). The garden is thus conceived here as a place for receiving wisdom.²⁴) Similarly, in the Garden Scene the queen and her garden may symbolize love, while Ashurbanipal may embody wisdom, since he is often praised for this feature in his royal inscriptions as received from Nabu.²⁵) In a fragmentary section of the text, Tashmetu also seems to be associated with a mural crown (*kilīlu*) (SAA 3 14: 21), while in the relief the queen Libbali-Sharrat wears a crown. Tashmetu is further associated with a bowl of lapis lazuli (SAA 3 14: r 12), which may recall the bowl held by the queen. The last section is focused on Tashmetu, who feels an inferiority to the counsellors and Nabu replies that her throne is the foremost among the counsellors, thus elevating her above all others (SAA 3 14: r 19, r 26). In parallel, in the Garden Scene the queen Libbali-Sharrat exceptionally occupies the throne on which the king would normally be seated. The latter is a unique example, and no Assyrian queen is depicted seating on a throne.²⁶) Finally, in the lyrics, birds twittering and fruits are mentioned; likewise, the grapes, the food, and the birds populating the Garden Scene may mark a visual transposition of these euphemistic expressions for love-making and erotic games.

The second textual comparison is offered by the text entitled by the editors as the *Sacred Marriage of Nabû and Tašmetu* (SAA 13 70). The main setting of this scene is the bedroom, where Nabu and Tashmetu enter together. The bedroom also features in the last section of the love lyrics (SAA 3 14: r 9). While they are still in the bedroom, it is said that the two gods are served with a royal banquet (SAA 13 70: 9–10), which may recall the one offered to Ashurbanipal and Libbali-sharrat in the Garden Scene. Later, the text says that Nabu goes on a hunt in the game park as part of the sacred marriage ritual (SAA 13 70: r 1–r 4): this incident

(GeMANE 5) which took place on 1st–3rd of June 2022 at the University of Helsinki and the Centre of Excellence in Ancient Near Eastern Empires. The paper is under preparation for the workshop proceedings volume (Zaphon, wEdge 2024) with the title “Un homme et une femme. Humanly Divine Love Affairs in the Garden Scene of Ashurbanipal”.

²³) This idea of protection is evoked also by the stepped motifs resembling the crenellations of the queen’s crown running along the borders of her robe and the tops of her shoes (in this respect, see Gansell 2014a: 411).

²⁴) For the meanings linked to the garden, see Lapinkivi 2004: 212–219. For a detailed analysis of the love lyrics and the metaphors used, see Nissinen 1998.

²⁵) In the introduction to his book (2–5), Reade equates the building designated as *bīt ridūti* in texts with the North Palace. For a different opinion, see Kertai 2015: 168–169. Ashurbanipal identifies the scribal arts that he learned in the crown prince’s House of Succession (*bīt ridūti*), probably the North Palace, as Nabu’s exclusive wisdom: “Furthermore, I, Ashurbanipal, learned inside it the wisdom of the god Nabû, all of the scribal arts. I investigated the precepts of every type of scholar there is, learned how to shoot a bow, ride a horse (and) chariot, (and) take hold of (their) reins”. (RINAP 5/1 9: i 24–i 28).

²⁶) Libbali-sharrat appears again seated on a throne in her stele from Assur (Portuese 2022: fig. 1).

may have been visually translated to the lower register of the Garden Scene, where Ashurbanipal himself is probably carrying out a hunt.²⁷) Alternatively, this textual reference might be depicted in the lion hunt located in the opposite wall to the Garden Scene, the north-west wall of Room X. This may imply that the moment in which the queen and the king relax together underneath the vine arbor takes place before the hunt, while the horse on the top register of relief FSB–7 (X–13) may be a shorthand for the lion hunt on the north-west wall.

There is another correspondence between the *Love Lyrics of Nabû and Tašmetu* and the Garden Scene that is worth underscoring. The key element that connects the two sources is the window, which is reconstructed in Room X as having two columns, replicating the one below in Room S, and located opposite the Garden Scene relief. As Reade observes, from Room X the royal “couple could have enjoyed the view through the window westward into the garden” (42).²⁸) The consequence of this is that the royal couple depicted in the scene was framed between the two hypothetical columns, as if they were perennially looking out of the window. If a window was present in this room and opposite the relief, a reference to it can be seen in both the love lyrics and the reliefs.

In the lyrics, as stated above, Tashmetu is associated with the mural crown, which is denoted by the word *kilīlu*. Although the text is fragmentary at this point, the word *kilīlu* may also recall the goddess or demoness Kilili, who is described as “the woman looking from the window” (*Kilili ša apāta ušarru*) in a first-millennium incantation corpus and equated with Ishtar in the same corpus.²⁹) Similarly, in the Garden Scene the image of a woman peering out of the window is reproduced by the woman-at-the-window motif engraved at the top of the couch’s leg where the king reclines. This motif seems to have been deliberately made visible through the throne of the queen. Therefore, a reference to the window is present both in the text and in the relief. If these observations are valid, there would be an interesting overlap between the text, image, and reality: the action alluded to in the text, depicted in the relief, and potentially performed in Room X perhaps all evoked the customary female norm of waiting for one’s spouse by the window.

In fact, the act of waiting by the window—far from prying eyes—in an amorous, protective, and attentive attitude in expectation of one’s lover’s appearance is often attested in Near Eastern literary love compositions.³⁰) As suggested by Suter (1992) in her analysis of the iconographic motif of the woman at the window, the window allows women to be detached and have reserved contact with the outside world, bridging the physical contact between the lovers and symbolizing the connection between the inside of the house and the outside world, between the sphere of activity of the woman and that of the man.³¹) This suggests that the woman-at-the-

²⁷) Albenda 1976: 69–70.

²⁸) As Reade points out in his book (22), the garden planted by Ashurbanipal was probably accessible through the north-west door of Room S.

²⁹) “Beschwörung: Du bist *kilili*, die sich durchs Fenster beugt” (Farber 1977: 64–65, A 1a 22). For Kilili as female demon, see CAD K, *kilili* 2, s.v. This observation was first made by Nissinen (1998: 610) and Lapinkivi (2004: 233) who both equated Kilili with Ishtar. Tashmetu is associated with the window in another text concerning the cultic topography of Assur (SAA 20 49: 4).

³⁰) Held 1961; Nissinen 1998: 602; George 2009: 71–75.

³¹) See also Gansell 2014b: 62–64; Winter 2016.

window motif depicted on the couch's legs is a reference to the window in Room X and the window apparently mentioned in the love lyrics, and it acted as a symbolic reference to the stages of courtship by the beloved that included sneaking into the woman's house and asking to be let in. This assumption further supports the idea that it is the queen Libbali-sharrat who invites her spouse Ashurbanipal to enter her abode and private space, and this may be the reason why she is the actual protagonist of the scene, just like Tashmetu in the love lyrics.³²⁾

Such reasoning also leads me to speculate on the function of the upper rooms. After discussing the reconstruction of these spaces, Reade concludes that "[t]his reconstruction of part of the upper storey leaves little space for the harem women's work spaces, wells and tombs that might have been expected in a royal palace, but this reflects the special status of the North Palace" (23). He then continues by suggesting that a women's quarter may have existed in the secluded space between Rooms A, E, R and the postulated Court AA. However, the amorous activities inferred from a combined reading of the sources rather suggest that Room X and the nearby rooms may have been available for some women of the royal household, especially the queen.³³⁾ Although the reliefs do not always reflect a specified use of the associated rooms and it would be unwarranted and misleading to label a decoration or architecture as "feminine" or "masculine", in this case all the available and reconstructed sources hint at this possibility.³⁴⁾ In fact, some activities may have been female-centered and both architecture and decoration could hint at functions and events that revolved around women. In this respect, the unique inscription dedicated by Sennacherib to Tashmetu-sharrat and inscribed on colossi stationed in an entrance to the queen's suite is illuminating: "Moreover, for Tašmētu-šarrat, the palace lady, my beloved spouse, whose form the goddess Bēlet-ilī made more perfect than (that of) all (other) women: I had a palatial hall for lovemaking, happiness, and exultation built, and (then) I stationed sphinxes of white limestone in its gates" (RINAP 3/2 40: 44"b–46"). From this textual reference, it seems that the queen's suite was a place for charm, seductiveness, lovemaking (*ru'āme*), joy (*hidāte*), and exultation (*rīštu*). This atmosphere is exactly echoed in Room X, in the Garden Scene reliefs, and in the *Love Lyrics of Nabû and Tašmetu*. Interestingly, Ashurbanipal asserts in his inscriptions that the bed is made for the lovemaking and the wedding of the divine couple and it is placed in the bed chamber of the goddess: "I skillfully mad[e] a bed of *musukkannu*-wood, a [dur]able wood, that is clad with *pašallu*-gold (and) [studded with] precio[us] stones, as a pleasure bed for the god Bēl (Marduk) and the god[dess] Bēltiya (Zarpanītu) to carry out the wedding (and) to make lo[ve]. I pla[ced] (it) in Kaḫilisu, the bed chamber of the goddess Zarpanī[tu], which is laden with sexual charm" (RINAP 5/1 7: i 7'–i 13'). This quotation provides an interesting parallel with the Garden Scene, since it states that the bed used for lovemaking by the divine couple was placed in

the bed-chamber of the goddess, just as the couch on which Ashurbanipal reclines is placed in a space that perhaps belonged to the queen. Therefore, there are plausible reasons to believe that Room X and the nearby rooms reconstructed by Reade were part of the queen's suite, where the king was sometimes invited as a special guest to spend his time with his wife, far from the stress of the kingly daily life, in order to reenact the divine encounter between Nabu and Tashmetu and assure the blessing and protection of the royal family.³⁵⁾ In this light, it would not seem too far-fetched to suppose that, when Ctesias refers to the Assyrian king as "seen by no one except his concubines and attendant eunuchs, and sought luxury and idleness", he is referring to this type of activity, with the consequence that, again, the last Assyrian kings were perceived as quasi-divine beings.

Abbreviations

- ABL: see Harper 1892–1914
 CAD: Assyrian Dictionary of the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago (1956–2010)
 SAA 1: see Parpola 1987
 SAA 3: see Livingstone 1989
 SAA 5: see Lanfranchi / Parpola 1990
 SAA 9: see Parpola 1997
 SAA 10: see Parpola 1993
 SAA 13: see Cole / Machinist 1998
 SAA 16: see Luukko / Van Buylaere 2002
 SAA 18: see Reynolds 2003
 SAA 20: see Parpola 2017
 RINAP 3/2: see Grayson / Novotny 2014
 RINAP 5/1: see Novotny / Jeffers 2018

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³²⁾ For the queen as the main protagonist of the Garden Scene, see Kertai 2020.

³³⁾ This possibility is also cautiously alluded to by Kertai (2015: 182).

³⁴⁾ The nearby rooms indicated by Reade as Z and Y probably contained military scenes (FSC and FSF series), a theme that should not surprise since the suite of the queen Tashmetu-sharrat in the Southwest Palace of Sennacherib was decorated with military scenes (Barnett et al. 1998: pls. 450–461).

³⁵⁾ The function of the rituals performed for this divine couple appears to be the protection and benediction of the king, the crown prince and the royal family. This is confirmed by some letters and texts which give accounts of a ritual performed for Nabu and Tashmetu (SAA 3 6; SAA 3 10; SAA 13 56; SAA 13 78; see also Nissinen 1998: 592–597; 2001: 110–113).

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